

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

A Case Report

CASE STUDY ON PARACOCOCCIDIOIDOMYCOSIS (DEEP MYCOSES)

¹ Iram Jalal, ² Mr. Muhammad Afzal, ³ Ms. Hajra Sarwar

¹. Student at Lahore School of Nursing, The University of Lahore, Pakistan

². Head of Department Lahore of School of Nursing

³. Lecturer Lahore School of Nursing

Article Received: March 2019

Accepted: April 2019

Published: May 2019

Abstract:

Fungal infection of the mouth (mycoses) have derived from specific noticeable quality from the start of the (AIDS), however furthermore, expanding on worldwide scale and expanded introduction to significant mycoses endemic, generally in the typical zone. Paracoccidioidomycosis is an uncommon disease worldwide yet an average significant mycoses in Brazil and some other endemic regions in Latin America. Lutz first depicted the sickness in 1908 out of two patients from the Sta Casa of Sao Paulo state, Brazil, with oral sores and cervical lymphadenopathy. Dermatophytosis\ tinea or ringworm of the skin, scalp, and nails is caused by the group of fungi known as dermatophytes. They each involve a particular environment and specific temperature, in molds the environment at the temperature of 25 degree C to 30 degree C and in yeast at body temperature. opportunistic mycoses are the fungal infection of the body which is happen in those patient whose normal defence mechanisms are impaired the increase incidence of these contamination because of low resistance level because of AIDs, malignant growth, and post-transplantation, cytotoxins, chemotherapy, corticosteroid and the use of antibiotics. In semi-private hospital of Lahore, The 12 year case report with deep mycoses on his face. On assessment, lesions of left cheek is wet with pus discharge. Pain on ankle, patient complaint cough with sputum, patient is complaint of fever for previous 2, 3 days after administration of amphotericin.B. Patient was vitally stable with no active issue B.P: 110\70, Pulse: 68\minute, Temperature: 98.6 F. The lab investigation of patient was: Hb: 11.7, TLC: 13.7, PLT count: 562, ESR: 87, Na: 134, K: 4.8. Mycoses run in degree from superficial contaminations including the external layer of the stratum corneum of the skin to spread disease including the cerebrum, heart, lungs, liver, spleen, and kidneys.

Keywords: fungal infection, oral-faecal rout, immunocompromised person

Corresponding author:**Iram Jalal,**

Lahore School of Nursing, The University of Lahore, Pakistan

E-Mail: Iramjalal007@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Iram Jalal et al., *Case Study On Paracoccidioidomycosis (Deep Mycoses),* Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(05).

INTRODUCTION: -

Fungal infection of the mouth (mycoses) have come into particular detectable quality coming from the (AIDS), however furthermore, expanding on worldwide scale and world travel have expanded introduction to significant mycoses endemic, generally in the tropics. Paracoccidioidomycosis is an uncommon disease worldwide yet a typical profound mycoses in Brazil and some other endemic regions in Latin America. Lutz first depicted the sickness in 1908 out of two patients from the Sta Casa of Sao Paulo state, Brazil, with oral sores and cervical lymphadenopathy. In 1912, Splendore called the parasite secluded by Lutz *Zymonema brasiliensis*. In 1930, Floriano Almeida showed that the organism was unmistakable from *Coccidioides immitis*, and named the family *Paracoccidioides brasiliensis*. (Paes Almeida, 2015). It is opportunistic organisms causing deep mycoses attacks a number of human body systems. Mycoses disease is can be due fungal agents. These fungi are eukaryotes and they have of cell wall. They grow in multicellular fibber's\ filaments called molds, and these fibber's\ filaments called hyphae. Hyphae are in round shaped, they are effectively turned out to be airborne numerous pathogenic parasites (fungi) who are forming hyphae, grow at surrounding temperature yet yeast grow at body temperature. The superficial fungal infection of the skin, hairs and nails no range of pathological changes take place in the host due to the infectious agent. (Kims, 2012). Subcutaneous mycoses are chronic localized infection of the skin and subcutaneous tissue these are happen because of traumatic injury. These causative growths\causative fungi are soil saprophytes, whose ability to adopt tissue environment. Endemic mycoses are caused by a heterogeneous group of fungi. They can cause infection in healthy host. They each involve a particular environment and specific temperature, in molds the environment at the temperature of 25 degree C to 30 degree C and in yeast at body temperature. The examples of endemic mycoses are: Blastomycosis, Histoplasmosis, Coccidioidiomycosis, penicilliosis, Paracoccidioidomycosis and sporotrichosis (Kims, 2012) opportunistic mycoses are the fungal infection of the body which is happen in those patient whose normal defence mechanisms are impaired the increase incidence of these contamination because of low resistance level because of AIDs, malignant growth, and post-transplantation, cytotoxins, chemotherapy, corticosteroid and the use of antibiotics. The examples of opportunistics mycoses are: cryptococcosis, candidiasis, zygomycosis (mucormycosis), and aspergilosis. Deep mycoses are caused by the primary

pathogenic and opportunistic fungal pathogen, the first systemic fungal pathogen include coccidioides immitis, histoplasma capsulatum, blastomyces dermatitidis, and paracoccidioides brasiliensis. (Walsh, 2014). Oral fungal infection (mycoses) may spread due to specific noticeable quality since the appearance of contamination with human immunodeficiency infection (HIV), and acknowledgment of the acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), just as the amazing introduction to diseases endemic in the tropics. (Paes Almeida, 2015) Paracoccidioidomycoses is acquired by respiratory route. The primary pulmonary disease in the greater part of the cases is oligosymptomatic, yet later it can scatter, including numerous organs, particularly mucous and cutaneous tissue, lymph nodes, adrenals, and the central system. (Lopes Colombo, 2014)

CASE PRESENTATION: -

In semi-private hospital of Lahore, The 12 year case report with deep mycoses on his face. Patient attendants verbalized that it was started from pimple and after some days it appears black and it spread of the face and then it spread and covers the extremities. As verbalized by attendants after medication it has been stopped but it was not cure completely. Patient said, this is very painful. All the time patient feel pain on his face and extremities. On pain scale 8\10 according to patient. After medication he feel pain free, and when the effect of medication was minimised the pain was started. On assessment patient attendants verbalized that patient was immunized. There were no previous surgery of the patient. Physically patient look fatigued, lethargic. Patient skin colour was pale and around the wound it looks black. Lesions present all over the face. Lesion of left cheek is wet with pusy discharge. Patient have no complaint of head, neck, ear, eyes, mouth, throat, problems. But patient have complaint of nasal congestion. Although patient have no complaint of thorax lungs, breast and lymphatic region, heart and neck vessels, abdomen, male genitalia, anus, rectum, and prostate problems. Pain have complaint of his extremities pain because of spread of mycoses bacterium. Extremities colour looks black like his face. Also patient feels muscular pain, patient feels he was not able to do his work properly. Psychologically patient was very depressive, and anxiety about his next life, patient thought "what happened next to me?" I feel lethargic when I do any work. On assessment, lesions of left check is wet with pus discharge. Pain on ankle, patient complaint cough with sputum, patient is complaint of fever for previous 2, 3 days after administration of amphotericin.B. Patient was vitally stable with no active issue B.P:

110\70, Pulse: 68\minute, Temperature: 98.6 F. The lab investigation of patient was: Hb: 11.7, TLC: 13.7, PLT count: 562, ESR: 87, Na: 134, K: 4.8.

Medical diagnosis:-

Deep mycosis is caused by fungus that can be attacks tissues cause superficial, subcutaneous, or systemic disease. painful ulceration and nodules show up in subcutaneous tissues in sporotrichosis (sporothrix). (Reich, 2012). Tinea pedis, normally interdigital type and toenail onychomycosis are critical hazard factors for 132w bacterial cellulitis of the lower legs. Dermatophytoses could be complicated by preseptal cellulitis. Candida species and malassezia species are the most vital pathogens in the induction of contagious sensitivity and might be in charge of unfavorably susceptible rhinitis, hypersensitive sinusitis, atopic asthma, urticaria, or unfavorably susceptible skin inflammation. A conclusion dependent on a single specimen and method, particularly when the outcomes are negative, in many situations, a single specimen and test strategy can't be depended upon for the diagnosis of a fungal infection. Without such information, results acquired by the utilization of nonculture methods, for example, direct examination, ordinary and immunohistologic staining, exoantigen identificatin, DNA hybridization, immunodiffusion, supplement obsession, compound immunoassay can permit distinguishing proof of the etiologic growth or give immunologic proof for a particular fungal infection. (Kaufman L, 1992). Wound or lesion clean with normal saline solution, and normal saline dressing. Injection fungizone (amfoterisin B) 25mg IV in 5%D\W 200ml one times a day. Injection 0.9% N\Saline 500ml IV before and after given injection fungizone. Applied Mupir (mupirocin) ointment on face and body. Tab atarax (hydroxyzine hydrochloride) 10mg P\O two times a day. Lotion oxoferion (terachlorodecaoxide) applied on face one times a day. Syrup Ibret (iron, vitamin C and B complex) 1TSF P\O one times a day. Tab chewcal (calcium+ vitamin D) P\O one times a day. Apply MMs (mometasone furoate) nasal spray two times a day. Syrup tricaine 1TSF P\O three times a day. Tab septran (co-trimoxazole) 480mg in morning time. (Shikanai-Yasuda, 2015)

Nursing diagnosis:-

Diseases happen when the defence mechanism of an individual are deficient to secure them. organism, for example, bacterium, virus, fungus, and different parasites attack defenseless has through inescapable wounds and exposures. Breaks in the covering of the skin, mucous films, delicate tissues, or even organs,

for example, the kidneys and lungs can be destinations for contaminations after injury, obtrusive techniques, or attack of pathogens through the circulatory system or lymphatic framework. Furthermore, a typical methods for irresistible illnesses caused by the prompt exchange of microbes, infections or different germs starting from one individual to another. This can come to pass by means of contact, airborne, sexual contact, or sharing of IV medicate stuff. Likewise, having insufficient assets, absence of information, and being malnourished spot a person at high danger of building up a contamination. Insufficient essential guards (e.g., broken skin integrity, tissue harm). Deficient learning to evade presentation to pathogens. These are the cautionary indications of disease. Any suspected oozing care to be process; anti-toxin treatment is dictated by pathogens recognized Color of respiratory discharges. Yellow or yellow-green sputum is demonstrative of respiratory disease and Raised temperature.

Figure no.1.1

CONCLUSION: -

Oral fungal infection (mycoses) have come from specific noticeable ability since the onset of (AIDS). This disease is expanding on worldwide level.

Mycoses of the mouth is an uncommon disease. Mycoses can occur due to fungal agent. Mycoses may spread due to contamination of immunodeficient with infected things. According to this case scenario this starts from a light pimple and because of patient is immunocompromised it is spread from pimple to oral fungal infection (mycoses). According to this case scenario and according to article this after giving medication it would be stop but not cure completely. It would be stopped by antifungal medications and that is: Fungizone, Itraconazole, Sulfadiazine, Amphotricine, etc.

REFERENCES:

1. Almeida, O. P., Jorge Junior, J., & Scully, C. Paracoccidioidomycosis of the mouth: an emerging deep mycosis. *Critical Reviews in Oral Biology & Medicine*, 14(4), 268-274.(2003)
2. Colombo, A. L., Queiroz-Telles, F., & Graybill, J. R. (2000). Paracoccidioidomycosis. In *Atlas of Infectious Diseases* (pp. 53-63). Current Medicine Group, London
3. In *Sequelae and Long-Term Consequences of Infectious Diseases* (pp. 407-413). American Society of Microbiology
4. Kim, M. S., Lee, S. M., Sung, H. S., Won, C. H., Chang, S., Lee, M. W., ... & Moon, K. C. (2012). Clinical analysis of deep cutaneous mycoses: a 12-year experience at a single institution. *Mycoses*, 55(6), 501-506
5. Kaufman, L. (1992). Laboratory methods for the diagnosis and confirmation of systemic mycoses. *Clinical infectious diseases*, 14(Supplement_1), S23-S29.
6. Reich, A., Schwartz, R. A., & Szepietowski, J. C. (2009). Complications of superficial mycoses.
7. Shikanai-Yasuda, M. A. (2015). Paracoccidioidomycosis treatment. *Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de São Paulo*, 57, 31-37.
8. Walsh, T. J., & Dixon, D. M. (1996). Spectrum of mycoses. *Medical microbiology*, 919-925